

Evidence Based Yoga Module for Improving Psycho-Physiological Health of Hypertension Patients

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Received : 03/03/2024

1st BPR : 08/03/2024

2nd BPR : 15/03/2024

Accepted : 22/03/2024

Abstract

Hypertension is a global disease but its prevalence varies amongst countries & sub-populations. The prevalence of hypertension increases with growing age & it is estimated that starting from around 15-20% in the early age, it increases to 75-80% in individuals above 70 years of age. All sections of the population in India suffer & its prevalence in urban population is higher compared to that of the rural population. Hypertension is a chronic condition of concern due to its role in the causation of CAD, stroke & other vascular complications. It is one of the major risk factors for cardio vascular mortality which accounts for 20-50% of all deaths. It is now a known fact that the health of the human being is influenced by various factors like attitude, beliefs, emotional states and lifestyle pattern. Therefore, just providing medicines is not sufficient. In order to provide long term relief, it is imperative that all the aspects of life and personality are taken into consideration. Yoga as a therapy caters to all the above requirements. The present research assesses the physical and emotional distress in hypertensive patients and how a tailored yoga can have a positive influence on that. This paper provides an ideal Yoga Module for hypertensive patients which can be used as an adjuvant to the current treatment plan.

Key words: Hypertension, CAD, Emotions, Attitudes, Lifestyle, Yoga.

Introduction

The present age is the age of speed. This speed has enabled the mankind to make speedy progress in every aspect of life. Also, this progress has increased his access to the facilities which can make his life comfortable while consuming lesser time. The materialistic approach has set itself within deepest belief systems of a man. The obsession with things and passion to acquire more and more materialistic comforts has made man himself a machine. There is no time to eat, drink, rest and entertain. But this type of fast lifestyle is now taking its toll. The results are increase in stress and stress related issues which are ultimately manifesting at the physical level in the form of psychosomatic problems. Scientists are now able to link a number of health problems with lifestyle. It is now a known fact that the health of the human being is influenced by various factors like attitude, beliefs, emotional states and lifestyle pattern. Therefore, just providing medicines is not sufficient. In order to provide long term relief, it is imperative that all the aspects of life and personality are taken into consideration. Thought processes, belief systems, stress, lifestyle pattern etc. can be the cause of origin for a number of health problems which may be physiological or psychosomatic. One such problem can be Hypertension.

Hypertension

Hypertension is a global disease but its prevalence varies amongst countries & sub-populations. The prevalence of hypertension increases with growing age & it is estimated that starting from around 15-20% in the early age, it increases to 75-80% in individuals above 70 years of age. All sections of the population in India suffer & its prevalence in urban population is higher compared to that of the rural population. Hypertension is a chronic condition of concern due to its role in the causation of CAD,

stroke & other vascular complications. It is one of the major risk factors for cardio vascular mortality which accounts for 20-50% of all deaths.

High blood pressure (hypertension) means that your blood is pumping with more force than normal through your arteries. There are two types of hypertension. For 95 percent of people with high blood pressure, the cause of their hypertension is unknown. This is called essential, or primary, hypertension. When a cause can be found, the condition is called secondary hypertension.

There is an urgent need to address this disease and search for suitable interventions which can be implemented at community levels. Hypertension is on rise since 1980. The incidence is 20 - 40% in urban & 12 - 17% in rural areas. According to Directorate General of Health Services, Ministry of Health and Family Welfare, Government of India, the overall prevalence of hypertension in India by 2020 was 159.46/1000 population. HTN requires the immediate use of medications, lifestyle changes are recommended in conjunction with medication. Because large segments of the hypertensive population are either untreated or inadequately treated, non-pharmacological, alternative therapies with potential BP-lowering effects, such as yoga, deserve research attention.

Over the past 25 years, the resources of health-care services have significantly risen in India and the country has adopted a universal health coverage program. Although the availability of health-care services has risen, the quality of treatment received from different health-care providers is not consistent. Inconsistent guidelines introduce uncertainty in the accuracy of hypertension diagnoses and increase the likelihood of poor health outcomes. Poor health-care literacy, high self-medication rate, poor blood pressure control and inconsistent hypertension management guidelines increase the problem in India.

With increase in the rate of hypertension a cost effective and easy method should be introduced to control the rising cases of hypertension and to replace the harmful conventional treatments. Some researchers have already worked and are working to establish the efficacy of home remedies and exercises in management of hypertension. This work aims at establishing yoga therapy as an accepted and effective system of treatment which can be used by the people suffering from hypertension. One of the main goals of yoga is to achieve tranquility of the mind and create a sense of well-being, feeling of relaxation, improved self-confidence, improved efficiency, increase attentiveness lowered irritability and have an optimistic outlook on life.

Yoga as a therapy:

Yoga is a holistic healing system that influences all these factors. These factors are Asanas or physical postures, proper breathing in the form of Pranayama or breath regulation, sufficient rest and relaxation through relaxation techniques, expansion of awareness & positive attitude through meditation and optimum nutrition through balanced yogic diet. Thus Yoga is an important natural preventive measure to ensure optimum health through moderation & regulation of lifestyle. Moreover, Yoga is a self-therapy in the sense that one can perform this discipline on one's own.

With a foresight of offering Yoga therapy as a safe, beneficial and cost effective therapy for Hypertension, the present study was conceived. The main objective of the study was to establish Yoga therapy for improving physical, mental and emotional health of mid aged hypertensive patients considering the current life style. The study aimed at teaching stress management and lifestyle correction techniques through yoga. This was conceived with a long term objective of reducing the risk of cardio-cerebro-vascular morbidity that are associated with elevated blood pressure.

Yoga Module

The tailored Yoga Module was designed after obtaining positive results in 100 hypertensive patient from Bhopal, both male and female patients between ages 40 to 60 years. After randomly assigning to two groups, following the acquisition of their written consent; experimental underwent a structured Yoga program for a duration of 90 days, whereas the Wait-listed Control group didn't receive yoga program. To assess the influence of yoga on hypertension, the Cornell Medical Index (C.M.I.) Health

Questionnaire was administered at two distinct points; before commencing the study and after its completion. The tailored Yoga Module consisted of Asanas, Pranayamas and Relaxation to assess the effects on the dependent variable, that is, Hypertension.

Data collected was analyzed using standard Data Analysis Tools using the JASP Software, 0.18.3 Version, such as Shapiro-Wilk's test, Mann Whitney U-Test and Paired sample analysis. The comparisons between the control group and experimental group were conducted to assess the significance of the data. On the basis of statistical analysis and subsequent interpretation, it was concluded that a tailored Yoga Module is effective in management of mental, emotional and physical distress in diagnosed hypertensive patients. These findings definitely pave a way towards establishing Yoga as an integrative therapy for hypertension. The Yoga Module used in the present work has been constructed while keeping in mind the whole spectrum of health of a hypertensive patients. As health is an interplay of physical, psychological, emotional and spiritual aspects, the entire or holistic personality of an individual has been considered while designing this module. The module is described below:

Yoga Module for a Hypertensive Patient

Duration	:	30-40 Minutes
Preferred Time of Practice	:	Morning 6-8 AM (Empty Stomach) or Evening 5-7 PM (3 hours after lunch)
Preferred Clothing	:	Loose and Comfortable Cotton Clothes
Requirements	:	A Yoga Mat, Drinking Water
Precautions	:	Take relaxation between asanas Practice under guidance Maintain regular practice Do not stop medications without physician's advice

Yoga Practice		Duration
Starting Prayer	ॐ सहना ववतु, सहनौ भुनक्तु, सहवीर्यम् करवावहै । तेजस्विनावधीतमस्तु, मा विद्विषा वहै ॥ ॥ॐ शांति: शांति: शांति: ॥ Aum! May He protect us both together; may He nourish us both together; May we work conjointly with great energy.	1 Minute
Asanas	A. Sitting Series <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ➤ Dandasan (Staff pose) ➤ Ardha padmasana (Half Lotus Pose) ➤ Padmasana (Lotus Pose) ➤ Vajrasana (The Thunderbolt Pose) ➤ Sukhasana or long sitting position for relaxing between the asanas B. Standing Series <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ➤ Vrikshasan (Tree Pose) C. Supine Series <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ➤ Ardha pavanamuktasana (Half Wind Release Pose) ➤ Pawanmuktasana (Wind Relieving Pose) ➤ Shavasana (The Corpse Pose) for relaxing between the asanas D. Prone Series <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ➤ Bhujangasana (The Cobra Pose) ➤ Shalabhasana (The Locust Pose) ➤ Makarasana (Crocodile Pose) for relaxing between the asanas 	1 Minute each with 30 seconds duration relaxation between the asanas
Relaxation Technique	Quick Relaxation Technique in Shavasana (or) Deep Relaxation Technique in Shavasana	5-10 Minutes 10 Minutes

Pranayama	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ➤ Anuloma Viloma Pranayama (Alternate Nostril Breathing) ➤ Bhramari Pranayama (The Humming Bee Breath) 	5 Minutes each
Meditation	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ➤ Ishtadev Dhyan (Meditation of desired deity) ➤ Tratak Dhyan (Meditation of candle flame) ➤ Om Chanting (Repetition of Omkara in mild sound) 	5 Minutes each
Concluding Prayer	<p>ॐ सर्वे भवन्तु सुखिनः सर्वे सन्तु निरामयाः । सर्वे भद्राणि पश्यन्तु मा कश्चिद्दुःखभाग्भवेत् । ॐ शान्तिः शान्तिः शान्तिः ॥</p> <p>May all sentient beings be at peace, may no one suffer from illness, May all see what is auspicious, may no one suffer. Om peace, peace, peace.</p>	1 Minute

Conclusion

There is sufficient objective evidence for Yoga therapy to be adopted as an adjuvant therapy for hypertension. This will reduce the prevalence of hypertension thereby reducing the burden on already struggling health care system in India where Doctor-Patient ratio is yet to reach a satisfactory mark. Yoga through its neuro-endocrinal mechanisms not only can prevent the disease in healthy population but can also delay complications in already hypertensive patients. Therefore, it is strongly suggested that yoga should be adopted as a compulsory therapy for both in-patient and out-patient health care facilities.

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